

NOTES

Co-ordination Complexes of *bis-π-cyclopentadienyl-* and *bis-π-indenyl Molybdenum(VI)-Oxo Dichlorides with 8-quinolinol*

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SOME π -cyclopentadienyl metal halides yield substitution derivatives with 8-quinolinol¹⁻³. In the present investigation, when an attempt was made to substitute chlorine atoms in *bis-π-cyclopentadienyl-* and *bis-π-indenyl molybdenum(VI)-oxo dichlorides* by an 8-quinolinolate group, quite unexpectedly, co-ordination complexes were obtained. Chlorine atoms in these compounds could not be substituted by 8-quinolinolate groups, even in presence of triethylamine.

Experimental

All precautions were taken to maintain anhydrous conditions during these preparations. *Bis-π-cyclopentadienyl* and *bis-π-indenyl molybdenum-oxo dichlorides* were prepared by the methods already reported^{4,5}. The elemental analysis of these complexes tallied satisfactorily with the compositions reported here.

Preparation of the complexes: *Bis-π-cyclopentadienyl-* or *bis-π-indenyl molybdenum-oxo dichloride* and 8-quinolinol (in the mole ratio of 1:2) were dissolved separately in THF and the solutions mixed. A green coloured precipitate was obtained. The resulting mixture was further refluxed for 5-6 hours to complete the reaction in each case. After partial concentration, the green precipitate was filtered off and was washed and dried under vacuum. The compositions of the compounds formed corresponded to the formulae $(C_5H_5)_2MoOCl_2 \cdot 2C_9H_7ON$ and $(C_9H_7)_2MoOCl_2 \cdot 2C_9H_7ON$.

Results and Discussion

Infrared spectra of the complexes were recorded in the region 4000-670 cm^{-1} on Perkin-Elmer Infracord, Model-137, Spectrophotometer in KBr pallets. The ir spectra of the adducts are quite similar to each other. The spectrum in each case consists of much sharper absorption bands than either of the

two reactants. These complexes show a broad band in the region 3700-3200 cm^{-1} with a maximum at 3500 cm^{-1} indicating the presence of intramolecular hydrogen bonding. The presence of quinoline ring is indicated by the usual bands⁶. A moderate band at 1600 cm^{-1} in 8-quinolinol splits into two very sharp bands at 1600 and 1575 cm^{-1} in these complexes. This shows the withdrawal of the lone pair of electrons from the 8-quinolinol through co-ordination⁷. Another sharp band at 1270 cm^{-1} for the free ligand, assigned to be due to $-OH$ and $N^+ - H$ bending modes, also splits into two very sharp bands at 1310 and 1250 cm^{-1} .⁸ Such splitting has also been observed in titanium tetrachloride-8-quinolinol adducts. A sharp band observed in the complexes at 1100 cm^{-1} is due to $C-O$ bending modes, characteristic of all 8-quinolinol derivatives⁹. A slight positive shift is also observed in the aromatic $C-H$ out-of-plane bending modes due to the tightening of the rings on complexation.

Many of the absorption bands due to π -cyclopentadienyl or π -indenyl groups have been masked by the 8-quinolinolate moiety. However, the spectrum patterns at 1030 cm^{-1} ($C-H$ in-plane deformation) indicate the presence of π -bonded cyclopentadienyl or indenyl rings. The $Mo=O$ stretching band is observed at a much lower frequency of 920 cm^{-1} , due to increased polarisation of $Mo=O$ bond on co-ordination of molybdenum with 8-quinolinol through nitrogen.

Taking the 8-quinolinol moiety as unidentate (owing to ready formation of the adducts)¹⁰, molybdenum seems to acquire a hepta co-ordination state in these adducts.

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Determination of Stability Constants of 5-Methyl-Salicylidene-*p*-Nitroaniline Complexes with Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺, Co²⁺ and Mg²⁺

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THE successive stability constants of the complexes of 5-methyl-salicylidene-*p*-nitroaniline with various bivalent metal ions have been determined potentiometrically following the Calvin-Bjerrum *pH* titration techniques as adopted by Irving and Rossotti¹.

The Corning Model 12, a precision research *pH* meter with a combined glass electrode and a calomel reference electrode was used for measuring 'B' values (*pH* meter readings) of the solutions. [H⁺] and *pH* values there from of the experimental solution were obtained from these B values using a standard calibration curve of [H⁺] vs *pH*. The changes in 'B' can be measured with an accuracy of 0.005 unit.

The ligand 5-methyl-salicylidene-*p*-nitroaniline was prepared by refluxing equimolar quantities of 5-methyl-salicylaldehyde and *p*-nitroaniline in methanol. The product was repeatedly crystallised from methanol (m.p. 167°).² The medium of titration was 75 : 25 percent (v/v) dioxan-water mixture. Sodium perchlorate was added to maintain a constant ionic strength. The titrations were carried out in nitrogen atmosphere. The free acid, the free acid plus the ligand and the mixture of metal ion containing acid plus the ligand were titrated against standard sodium hydroxide (1.04 M). Metal perchlorates were prepared from metal salts of A.R. grade, using perchloric acid of A.R. grade. All the solutions were standardised complexometrically³ by E.D.T.A. titrations. The experimental details and computational methods are the same as described in the earlier communication⁴. The experimental method of Irving and Rossotti¹ was applied to find out the values of \bar{n} and *pL*. The titrations were performed in duplicate to test the reproducibility.

It may be stated here that the reagent does not undergo hydrolysis under the experimental conditions described. This was indicated by the *tlc* taken from time to time of a sample titration mixture.

Since only one proton (of the phenolic OH group) per ligand molecule is liberated during complexation, 'Y', the number of dissociable protons attached to each ligand molecule is one.

The formation curve was obtained by plotting \bar{n}_A values against *pH* (Fig. 1) and is wave like. It extends over a range of 0.135 < \bar{n}_A < 0.995. The value of *pK*₁² which corresponds to the association of

Fig. 1. Formation curve of 5-methyl-salicylidene-*p*-nitroaniline.

proton to phenoxide ion of the reagent was evaluated from the half-integral point at $\bar{n}_A = 0.5$. This was further corroborated from the plot of $\log \left[\frac{\bar{n}_A}{1 - \bar{n}_A} \right]$ vs *pH*.

\bar{n} and *pL* values were calculated and \bar{n} values were plotted against corresponding *pL* values to get the formation curve of metal complex ion equilibria (Fig. 2) from which the values of stability constants $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were evaluated; these correspond to *pL* value at $\bar{n} = 0.5$ and 1.5 respectively. The values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were further corroborated from the plots of $\log \left[\frac{\bar{n}}{1 - \bar{n}} \right]$ vs *pL* and $\log \left[\frac{2 - \bar{n}}{\bar{n} - 1} \right]$ vs *pL* respectively.

The most representative values are recorded in Table 1. The order of stabilities of the bivalent metal chelates was found to be Cu²⁺ > Ni²⁺ > Co²⁺